

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 40**

SSHOC Training Toolkit (preliminary version)

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Task	T6.4 Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training Network
Version	V1.0
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Abstract

This milestone report describes the first release of the SSHOC Training Toolkit which was launched on April 20th, 2020. The Toolkit is meant for SSH trainers to find and retrieve materials that can be used in training activities.

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Note on the terminology

Please note that while the original title of the toolkit mentioned in the grant proposal and agreement was “SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Toolkit” rather than “SSHOC Training Toolkit”, it was decided to adapt the name to “SSHOC Training Toolkit” as it more accurately describes the content of the toolkit and its use. The Toolkit is directed at SSH trainers, but next to train-the-trainer materials, the toolkit also contains information on other learning and training materials available for the SSH community. The development of the toolkit was based on an already performed inventory for SSH learning materials (D6.7) and the collected information was of use to SSH trainers and the SSH community as well. Therefore, it was decided by task 6.4 to adjust the name of the toolkit to better reflect its content and potential use. The term “SSHOC Training Toolkit” is hence used in the milestone name and in the SSHOC online communication.

1. Introduction

Task 6.4 of SSHOC Work Package 6 concerns the building of expertise within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) training community. One of the key outcomes of this task and the milestone described in this report is the SSHOC Training Toolkit. The Toolkit is meant to serve as a framework for training design, organisation and delivery. It is developed to aid trainers in the SSH by providing them with materials that they can utilize in their own training activities. The Toolkit is a key resource for the SSHOC Training Community (described in more detail in *SSHOC Deliverable 6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community*) and will be promoted and used during the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps (described in more detail in *SSHOC Deliverable 6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community* and *D6.9 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)*).

The first version of the Training Toolkit was developed by extending the work from WP6 Task 6.3 which collected information on existing learning materials in the field of SSH. As described in *D6.7 Inventory of Existing Learning Materials*, a drupal-based application was used to collect and curate information on different learning materials. The same application was used and further extended to become the published first version of the SSHOC Training Toolkit that scholars can now freely access. The Toolkit is a searchable inventory that by the time of launch contained more than 70 items from 41 different sources covering a range of topics including

Research Data Management, Open Science and didactics. The Toolkit and its content are described in more detail in SSHOC *Deliverable D6.9 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)*.

Throughout the remainder of the SSHOC Project, the Toolkit will be further developed in collaboration with the SSHOC Training Community and presented and evaluated during the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps. A final version of the Toolkit is another milestone of the project later in the project (*Milestone 41 SSHOC Training Toolkit (updated version)*) and the final version will be described in SSHOC *Deliverable 6.11 SSHOC Training Toolkit (final)*.

2. Description of the Milestone

The toolkit was launched on April 20th 2020¹ (see Figure 1) and is since then accessible to the public at SSHOC official Website: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the news item announcing the launch of the SSHOC Training Toolkit.

The first iteration of the Toolkit is a **searchable inventory of materials** relevant for trainers in the SSH. As described in more detail in *D6.9 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)*, to establish this inventory, members of Task

¹ Link to the news item on the Toolkit <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-launches-toolkit-trainers-social-sciences-and-humanities> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

6.4 first collected a number of relevant sources providing materials for trainers. The term *source* in this case refers to an organisation, group or project that provides learning or training materials for trainers. The individual learning or training materials that are provided by the organisation, group or project are called *items* in the Toolkit and in this milestone report.

The identification of sources for the Toolkit built on the work that was performed for *D6.7 Inventory of Existing Learning Materials*. Several of the sources that were identified by the team working on D6.7 also provided materials dedicated to trainers and were thus included in the curation process for the train-the-trainer materials in the Toolkit. In addition, the team for task 6.4 identified new sources that were added and curated in the inventory and became part of the first iteration of the Toolkit.

At the time of launch, the Toolkit listed over **70 materials from 41 different sources** in various formats, such as modules, slides, games, videos and other items. Materials cover a range of topics including Research Data Management, FAIR data, text encoding, Open Science, and quantitative analysis, as well as didactics for better development and implementation of training activities.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The Training Toolkit is an important resource for the SSHOC Training Community and one of the **key outputs of Work Package 6**. While there are many organisations that offer educational materials for trainers in the field of SSH, it was thus far challenging to find these materials. The SSHOC Training Toolkit is meant to **provide a curated inventory** of these available train-the-trainer materials that allows trainers to find and retrieve them easily through one point of access. The Toolkit brings together information about the train-the-trainer materials developed and provided by the different SSHOC partners (like CESSDA or DARIAH) as well as other relevant training nodes that the project has identified (like OpenAIRE or EOSC-Hub), and other sources that offer materials dedicated to trainers.

The content of the Toolkit will be further extended throughout the project by adding more sources and items, as well as by including materials developed by the SSHOC project itself. The SSHOC Training Community will play an important role in the updated version of the Toolkit. They will be asked to use the Toolkit and provide feedback. In addition, the Training Community will also be asked to contribute materials and share their experiences on developing trainings for the SSH community using train-the-trainer resources. An important point of contact will be the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps. Over the course of the project, three Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps will be organized which will be used to present and collect feedback on the Toolkit, as well as to help trainers use the Toolkit to develop and improve their own training skills and activities. Due to the COVID19-crisis, Task 6.4 is working on taking elements of the bootcamps (originally planned as face-to-face events but cancelled) online to gather feedback for the Training Toolkit in this way. Face-to-face bootcamps will be organized later in 2020, if possible, and in 2021 once the COVID19-crisis has been defeated.

2.2. Means of verification

The toolkit was launched on April 20th 2020² and is available to the public on SSHOC official website: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the main page of the Toolkit.

The SSHOC Training toolkit provides an inventory of SSH training materials. More information can be found on the [SSHOC Training website](#).

Search entities

Displaying 1 - 117 of 117

Source			
ID	Title	Description	Curated topics
232	Alison	Alison is one of the world's largest free learning platforms for education and skills training.	Didactics
43	CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	The Data Management Expert Guide is designed by European experts from the CESSDA Training Working Group to	Didactics , Research data management/FAIR data

Entity type

- Item (76)
- Source (41)

Collections

- Training Toolkit (117)

Figure 2. Screenshot of the main page of the SSHOC Training Toolkit

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

There was an agreed change of the delivery date of this milestone and the related deliverable *D6.9 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)* from February 2020 to April 2020. See SSHOC GA Amendment-823782-16.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The first version of the SSHOC Training Toolkit has been launched successfully in April 2020. In the coming months, the Toolkit and its materials will be promoted, and feedback will be gathered from the trainers who use the Toolkit. The Toolkit will be extended and improved in collaboration with the SSHOC Training

² Link to the news item on the Toolkit <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-launches-toolkit-trainers-social-sciences-and-humanities> [accessed on 29th of April 2020]

Community. Dedicated events will be organized to present and discuss the Training Toolkit and facilitate input and feedback from the Training Community. These events include the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps as well as virtual meetings and presentations at other occasions.

List of figures

[Figure 1. Screenshot of the news item announcing the launch of the SSHOC Training Toolkit.](#)

[Figure 2. Screenshot of the main page of the SSHOC Training Toolkit](#)